

PROS AND CONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN LEARNING LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article gives information about pros and cons of AI in learning languages. The aim is to explain how AI can make the learning effective by differentiating advantages and disadvantages of it. The study is based on real-life evidences of AI in classrooms. Results have been shown that artificial intelligence can help to gain interactive practice, provide with faster feedbacks at the same time. However, findings also prove that AI can not provide with emotional conversations which we can gain from people. Furthermore, people who are learning languages with the help of AI, can result in a lack of creativity in their life.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, language learning, advantage, disadvantage, users, learners.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются преимущества и недостатки использования искусственного интеллекта в изучении языков. Цель исследования — объяснить, как ИИ может повысить эффективность обучения за счёт анализа его положительных и отрицательных сторон. Исследование основано на реальных примерах применения ИИ в учебных классах. Результаты показывают, что искусственный интеллект помогает получать интерактивную практику и обеспечивает более быструю обратную связь. В то же время, полученные данные доказывают, что ИИ не может обеспечить эмоциональное общение, которое возможно при взаимодействии с живыми людьми. Кроме того, у людей, изучающих язык с помощью ИИ, может наблюдаться снижение творческих способностей в жизни.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, изучение языков, преимущество, недостаток, пользователи, учащиеся.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is becoming more and more popular especially in the field of education. This article explores how AI supports students as it helps save time, gives personalized feedback while there are some downsides. The topic is relevant to the conference theme, as it focuses on new technology in education and its benefits and bad sides for learners and teachers.

The main aim of paper is that showing the good and bad sides of AI in learning languages. Although AI has changed our lives, some might argue that it

is for goodness. Many students can face difficulties when they start learning new language especially in speaking part. AI can support them by checking homeworks, practicing speaking faster and easier anytime and anywhere.

AI can support learners by offering things which is adapted based on each individuals' needs. For instance, one of the smart artificial intelligence is CHGPT. It can answer any kind of questions which interest students, depending on their native language or learning languages. Learners can ask grammar topics, it gives wide variety of materials, if they do not be satisfy the answer, they may ask again. Such kind of AI is helpful students to learn topics widely because it keeps the students satisfied without becoming tough or tedious. 'The promise of this technology is a higher quality of life for everyday users ' says Dylan Losey, assistant professor of Virginia Tech university.

One of the advantages of AI is practicing interactively. Chatbots and voice recognition systems allow speaking and listening practice in a realistic way. Chatbot is a program that can talk with the learner in writing or through speech. In language learning chatbots are used to help students practice speaking and writing. Doctor Philippa Hardman, a learning scientist at the University of Cambridge, used AI chatbots to guide students through writing tasks to help them brainstorm ideas, organize their thoughts and improve their grammar and vocabulary. And research shows that AI like chatbots have increased students' engagement and motivation.

Another main advantades is AI is that it can support a lot of users. Therefore users can not struggle with time problems. For example, if we ask questions from teachers, they may not have extra time to explain one topic again individually. Considering such kind of problems John McCarthy, who is inventor of artificial intelligence (1927-2011), offered a conception called 'timesharing'. Timesharing is a concept in computer systems that allow multiple users to use simultaneously the resource of a single computer. To put it simply, each user is separated small time slices rapidly, the speed is so high that it seems as if user is utilizing the computer alone. Results show that nowadays, this prinsiples are used in apps like Google Drive, Microsoft 365, CHatgpt and millions of users use such kind of system at the same time.

However, artificial intelligence is influencing our decision making. There is a potential risk of diminishing critical thinking skills as a lot of users depend on too much AI. As a result, as they rely on artificial intelligences like chatgpt, they do not want to suffer themselves. Therefore, most language learners struggle with lack of ideas in speaking or writing. Eugenia Rho, who is assistant professor of Virginia Tech University, claimed that 'these models are starting to bridge gaps in areas we traditionally reserved fot human touch, but it is important to remember they are still tools, not replacements.

Another disadvantage is losing human interaction. As we start to converse with AI, there is a question among people "should we interact with people". In order to learn new language of course we should be connected with

people. Because the more we speak, the more we can improve the language. If we do not interact with people we lose our ability to speak even in our native language.' Hence , it is crucial that we discuss how to set guardrails and ethical standards for the deployment and use of AI , ensuring they are used to enrich our lives rather than diminish the essence of human connection . While AIs bring challenges, they also offer unprecedented opportunities. It is up to us to harness their capabilities responsibly.

In conclusion, AIs bring wide range of opportunities to the field of education; gives quicker personalized feedbacks and have timesharing concept and so on. Nevertheless, disadvantages like lack of human connection and decisions. Hence, considering disadvantages of it , we should think that AIs are being used to manipulate or deceive us. Therefore , I consider its disadvantages outweigh its advantages.

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